

Tzintzuntzan

By José Luis Punzo Díaz, Instituto Nacional de Antropología e Historia

Entry tags: Mesoamerican Religions, Archaeological Site, Religious Group, Mesoamerica, West México, City, Tarascan, Religious Place, Archaeological monument

The pre-Hispanic city of Tzintzuntzan, on the shores of Lake Patzcuaro, was the capital of the Señorío Tarasco, an important pre-Hispanic empire that was a fierce rival of the Mexica, and dominated a vast territory of western Mexico of more than 75,000 square kilometers, during the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries. It was inhabited by the Señores Uacúsechas -Lord Eagles-, leaders of this señorío who ruled it through a hereditary dynasty. Tzintzuntzan functioned as its capital, ritual city, regional market and possessed a basic, ritual and elite craft production, containing the most important ritual spaces and being the royal residence of the ruler named calzonci (Pollard 2009: 242). The particularity of the conquest of Michoacán, which was agreed upon in its most important part, made this city a place where the Tarascan nobility coexisted with the Spanish conquerors for a good part of the 16th century in the old site of the city, gradually losing its importance during the 16th century to the neighboring Pátzcuaro. Thus, Tzintzuntzan is a unique place for the study of the transition from pre-Hispanic societies to those of the early colonial period, since, from being a pre-Hispanic capital and then a colonial city, it was quickly abandoned, leaving multiple archaeological remains on the hillsides that have not yet been fully studied.

Date Range: 1350 CE - 1522 CE

Region: Tarascan territory 16th century

Region tags: Mexico

The maximum extent of the Irechekua -empire- of Tzintzuntzan in the 16th century

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: - Pollard, H. P. (1972). Prehispanic urbanism at Tzintzuntzan, Michoacán.
- Source 2: - Castro-Leal, M. (1986). Tzintzuntzan Capital de los Tarascos (anonymous, Ed.). Gobierno del Estado de Michoacán.
- Source 3: - Oliveros-Morales, A. (2011). Tzintzuntzan Capital del reino purépecha (Fideicomiso). Fondo de Cultura Económica-Colegio de México.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://mediateca.inah.gob.mx/islandora_74/islandora/object/sitioprehispanico%3A2296
- Source 1 Description: Mediateca INAH is the open access digital repository of the National Institute of Anthropology and History of Mexico through which it makes its cultural and historical heritage available to the public..
- Source 2 URL: <https://lugares.inah.gob.mx/es/zonas-arqueologicas/zonas/1746-tzintzuntz%C3%A1n.html>
- Source 2 Description: Lugares INAH in the case of Tzintzuntzan is an official microsite where updated information about the archaeological site is included.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1938-2023

Notes: 1937-1938 Alfonso Caso y Jorge Acosta 1939-1946 Daniel Rubín de la Borbolla 1962-1978 Román Piña Chán 1972 Helen Pollard 1982 Román Piña Chán y Rubén Cabrera 1992 Efraín Cárdenas – Eugenia Fernández 2001 – 2011 Arturo Oliveros 2011-2012 Nelly Robles y Olga Landa 2019-2023 José Luis Punzo

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Instituto Nacional de Antropología e Historia

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation
- Tree, grove, or forest
- Body of water (as distinct from source)

Type of elevation

– Hill

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

- ↳ Type of feature
 - Terracing

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

- ↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:
Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?
 - No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

- ↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:
 - Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Field doesn't know

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

- ↳ A single structure
 - No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: It is part of a great pre-Hispanic city. It contains several pyramids, large platforms, and terraces. More than 1000 architectural elements have been identified.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Other [specify]: The main square and the pyramidal structures, which are open to the public, were important places to perform the most important rituals of the city.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Curicaueri the major god of the Tarsacan and the other four important gods in the main platform, and the city was consagrated to Xaratanga other important goddes for the Tarascans.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Notes: The ruler Tarsacus -Cazonci- had more than 2,000 builders to make houses and 1,000 to make temples.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Revealed by high god

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: The appearance of Xaratanga, an important goddess, to an important Tarasco-Uacusecha leader, Tannganxoan, prompts him to rebuild the city for her.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 93650

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 0

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: The coverings of the pyramids are made with rocks locally called Xanamus, which were cut and assembled on the entire facade.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

↳ Exposure to the elements:

– Yes

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

↳ Other intensive (time/resources expended) treatment [Specify]:

– Other [specify]: There exists a big ossuary in the main platform

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– Yes

↳ Human:

– Yes

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Yes

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Yes

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Historical sources mention the royal tombs that were located in front of the main pyramids.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: One of the representations of Curicaueri is in human form in the Relación de Michoacán.

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– Yes

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– Yes

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– Yes

Notes: The representation of Curicuaeri, the most important god, is a large obsidian knife.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice:

– Yes [specify]: Human sacrifices were systematically performed at the site.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: The supernatural beings expected that there would always be fires burning at the top of the pyramids and both fire and smoke were part of their food.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

- ↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
 - Yes

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

- Are sacrifices performed at this place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are there human sacrifices:
 - Yes

- ↳ Adults
 - Yes

- ↳ Is biological sex available from evidence:
 - Male
 - Female

- ↳ Children
 - Yes

- ↳ Foreigners and/or slaves
 - Yes

- ↳ Elites
 - No

- Are material offerings present:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are material offerings mandatory:
 - No

- ↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:
 - Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests

– Yes

↳ Local elites

– Yes

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: In the Gran Plataforma

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– I don't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– I don't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No